

Research

Advancing Robotic Automation: Real-Time Environmental Control Strategies for Planar Serial COBOTs

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Abstract: This research study proposes a unique method based on real-time environmental control for RRR planar serial redundant COBOT control, with the goal of improving safety and adaptability. Our work primarily focuses on the RRR planar manipulator, which allows for two-dimensional mobility thanks to its three revolute joints. The control scheme monitors and analyzes the environment in real time by integrating sensors such as force/torque, proximity, and vision systems. By using feedback, the manipulator's direction, velocity, and forces are dynamically changed in real-time in reaction to shifting environmental variables.

The control method combines path planning, collision avoidance, and feedback control to produce instantaneous commands. This makes it possible to interact with items and avoid barriers in a safe and effective manner. By reducing the likelihood of mishaps and enabling efficient operation in fluid, unstructured environments, this tactic improves versatility, productivity, and safety.

The research has the potential to significantly enhance intelligent and self-governing adaptation in numerous fields, including manufacturing, assembly, and cooperative robotics. As sensing technologies, control algorithms, and computer capabilities advance, so does the possibility for real-time environmental-based control strategies for RRR planar manipulators in the context of current industrial automation. It appropriately responds to reviewer criticism and lays the foundation for the development of more capable and effective robotic systems under complex and dynamic conditions.

Keywords: Robot Automation, Planar Serial Cobots, Real-Time Control, Obstacle Avoidance, Safety Enhancement

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Introduction

Robotic manipulators have become essential across industrial domains due to their precision, efficiency, and flexibility. However, enabling manipulators to dynamically interact with unstructured environments and humans safely remains an open challenge [1]. Developing effective control strategies that integrate multi-sensory feedback for safe physical collaboration is critical [4] [3]. This paper introduces a methodology for the dynamic modeling and motor integration to facilitate responsive environmental interaction [2].

Our research aims to develop and experimentally validate an environmental-aware reactive control strategy for safe human-robot collaboration using a 3-degree-of-freedom (DOF) RRR robotic manipulator [6]. The objectives are to:

- Derive the dynamic model incorporating DC motor dynamics,
- Design a responsive torque controller,
- Integrate proximity and vision sensing, and
- Implement collision avoidance and adaptive force regulation behaviors.

This research will help overcome limitations in sensing, modeling, and control that currently restrict the widespread adoption of human-robot co-working systems. Our paper offers a fresh approach to global path planning for redundant manipulators. A Newton-Raphson type algorithm is utilised to determine the solution to the path planning problem, which is presented as a finite time nonlinear control problem. The algorithm can handle various objective task definitions as well as joint and task space limits. The technique shows promising results in planning joint path sequences to meet Cartesian goal planning and path following while 13 smoothly tolerating posture changes. It also provides solutions for cyclic paths with recurrent joint patterns.

This research will significantly advance real-time physical collaboration between humans and manipulators by enhancing safety and intuitiveness [9]. The proposed methods can expand applications of collaborative robots across manufacturing, service, healthcare, and other domains requiring close contact interactions [7][5].

Methodology

Robots are widely used for pick-and-place activities, improving quality and production. The process includes hardware design, machine vision, control implementation, and path and trajectory planning. Hardware design begins with CAD modeling. The motor specs are then determined using this CAD model.

Inverse and forward kinematic modeling convert image processing-derived x and y coordinates into motor feedback angles. We then build the control mechanism to manage our articulations' velocity and spatial orientation. After control, the manipulator needs a smooth path to its goal. This is done through path and trajectory planning. All system operations will be closed-loop [10].

Fig 1. Flowchart of Cobot

CAD's Role in Industrial Automation

Computer-aided design and manufacturing have advanced industrial automation. Before starting manufacturing, a product's design must be perfect. This prevents delays from product changes.

Due to its many advantages over manual drawings, CAD has become essential in modern design markets.

Fig 2. CAD model of 3DOF (RRR) COBOT on solidWorks

Table 1: Material specification and lengths of the link

Material	Aluminum
Link 1	260 mm
Link 2	200 mm
Link 3	120 mm
Total Length	822 mm

Stress analysis

Stress analysis refers to the detailed inspection and assessment of internal forces and deformations within a structure or component when subjected to external loads. Structural and mechanical engineers employ stress analysis techniques

to ensure buildings, machines, and infrastructure can withstand anticipated loads without catastrophic failure or excessive deformation. There are numerous methods available for calculating or approximating the stress and strain in a structure, ranging from sophisticated numerical techniques like finite element analysis to manual analytical computations using mathematical formulas and principles. The overarching goal of any stress analysis is to map out the distributions of stress and deformation in a structure and compare these to prescribed limits and thresholds. Comprehensive stress analysis provides critical insight that informs the design and optimization of structures for safety, reliability, and performance. By understanding where stress concentrations develop within a structure, engineers can detect flaws and failure points, evaluate design modifications, and make data-driven decisions regarding material selection, geometric dimensions, and load conditions. The ability to accurately predict and visualize the stress state in a structural system enables the refinement and fortification of designs, dramatically improving overall quality and structural integrity. In essence, stress analysis is an indispensable tool for developing robust structures and mechanical components that can withstand their intended service loads without excessive deformation or failure.

Fig 3. Static stress analysis

Fig 4. Static displacement analysis

Fig 5. Dynamic stress analysis

Fig 6. Dynamic displacement analysis

Kinematics

Manipulator kinematics studies manipulator motion without force. Kinetics, which studies robot motion and joints and connections, is a key topic of robotics study. By examining robot joints and links' geometric features, Kinematics predicts robot movement and interactions. The topic of discussion is the environment.

Position Kinematics

Position kinematics is a subfield of robotics that deals with the determination of the location of a robot's end effector within its workspace, given the joint angles of the robot. It is a fundamental tool in robotics and is used in a wide variety of applications, including robot path planning, robot control, robot simulation, and robot vision.

Forward Kinematics

Forward kinematics is a specific type of position kinematics that involves predicting the position and orientation of the end effector, given the position and orientation of each joint of the robot. It is used to determine where the end effector will be located after a sequence of joint movements.

Applications

Forward kinematics is used in a wide variety of robotic applications, including:

- Robot path planning: Forward kinematics is used to calculate the trajectory of the end effector as it moves from one point to another.
- Robot control: Forward kinematics is used to calculate the joint angles required to move the end effector to a

desired location.

- Robot simulation: Forward kinematics is used to simulate the motion of a robot in a virtual environment.
- Robot vision: Forward kinematics is used to calculate the position and orientation of the end effector relative to a camera, which is useful for tasks such as object picking and placement.

Table 2: DH Parameters

No.	Link Length (l)	Link Twist (α)	Link Offset (d)	Link Angle (θ)
1	L ₁	0	0	θ ₁
2	L ₂	0	0	θ ₂
3	L ₃	0	0	θ ₃

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_i & -s\theta_i c\alpha_i & s\theta_i s\alpha_i & l_i c\theta_i \\ s\theta_i & c\theta_i c\alpha_i & -c\theta_i s\alpha_i & l_i s\theta_i \\ 0 & s\alpha_i & c\alpha_i & d_i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Transformation matrices for our manipulator are

$$T_1^0 = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & -s_1 & 0 & l_1 c_1 \\ s_1 & c_1 & 0 & l_1 s_1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$T_3^2 = \begin{bmatrix} c_3 & -s_3 & 0 & l_3 c_3 \\ s_3 & c_3 & 0 & l_3 s_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$T_3^0 = T_1^0 T_2^1 T_3^2 = \begin{bmatrix} c_{123} & -s_{123} & 0 & l_1 c_1 + l_2 c_{12} + l_3 c_{123} \\ s_{123} & c_{123} & 0 & l_1 s_1 + l_2 s_{12} + l_3 s_{123} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

End-effector's position can be determined using following equations

$$X = l_1 c_1 + l_2 c_{12} + l_3 c_{123}$$

$$Y = l_1 s_1 + l_2 s_{12} + l_3 s_{123}$$

$$Z = 0$$

In the case of a planar manipulator, where Z is zero, the desired end-effector position can be achieved using only two coordinates:

X and Y

The manipulator's motion is constrained to a two-dimensional plane, and thus the focus is solely on determining the X and Y coordinates to reach the desired position.

$$\theta = \theta_1 + \theta_2 + \theta_3$$

Where, θ is the angle of end effector from the base frame.

Inverse Kinematics

Inverse kinematics involves determining the joint angles when provided with a desired end-effector/gripper position. In this process, the link lengths are denoted as 'l1', 'l2', and 'l3'. By utilizing mathematical calculations and geometric relationships, we can find the appropriate joint angles that will enable the manipulator to reach the desired position of the end-effector.

- Desired joint angles = $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$
- Given end-effector/gripper position = X, Y, Z

$$\theta_2 = \cos^{-1} \frac{X_o^2 + Y_o^2 - L_1^2 - L_2^2}{2L_1L_2}$$

$$\tan \beta = \frac{\sin \beta}{\cos \beta} = \frac{L_2 \sin \theta_2}{L_1 + L_2 \cos \theta_2}$$

$$\tan \gamma = \frac{X_o}{Y_o}$$

$$(\gamma - \beta) = \theta_1$$

$$\theta_1 = \tan^{-1} \frac{X_o^2 + Y_o^2 - L_1^2 - L_2^2}{2L_1L_2}$$

$$Y_1 = Y_0 + L_3 \sin \theta_1 \theta_2 \theta_3$$

$$X_1 = X_0 + L_3 \cos \theta_1 \theta_2 \theta_3$$

$$\xi = \theta_1 + \theta_2 + \theta_3$$

Velocity Kinematics

Jacobian

Velocity kinematics involves assigning a given velocity to the joints of the manipulator and subsequently determining the velocity of the end-effector.

$$T_1^0 = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & -s_1 & 0 & l_1 c_1 \\ s_1 & c_1 & 0 & l_1 s_1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad T_2^0 = \begin{bmatrix} c_{1+2} & -s_{1+2} & 0 & l_1 c_1 + l_1 c_{12} \\ s_{1+2} & c_{1+2} & 0 & l_1 s_1 + l_2 s_{12} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$T_3^0 = \begin{bmatrix} c_{123} & -s_{123} & 0 & l_1 c_1 + l_2 c_{12} + l_3 c_{123} \\ s_{123} & c_{123} & 0 & l_1 s_1 + l_2 s_{12} + l_3 s_{123} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The position vectors are provided as follows:

$$O_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad O_1 = \begin{bmatrix} l_1 c_1 \\ l_1 s_1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad O_2 = \begin{bmatrix} l_1 c_1 + l_1 c_{12} \\ l_1 s_1 + l_2 s_{12} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$O_3 = \begin{bmatrix} l_1 c_1 + l_2 c_{12} + l_3 c_{123} \\ l_1 s_1 + l_2 s_{12} + l_3 s_{123} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The orientation vectors are given as follows:

$$Z_0 = Z_1 = Z_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow J\omega_1 = J\omega_2 = J\omega_3$$

$$Jv_1 = Z_0 \times (O_3) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} l_1c_1 + l_2c_{12} + l_3c_{123} \\ l_1s_1 + l_2s_{12} + l_3s_{123} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$Jv_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -l_1s_1 - l_2s_{12} - l_3s_{123} \\ l_1c_1 + l_2c_{12} + l_3c_{123} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

GUI designed for position kinematics

An intuitive GUI was developed in MATLAB to allow interactive input of desired end-effector poses and visualization of the resulting manipulator configurations. The GUI provides a user-friendly tool for synthesizing and analyzing position kinematics without requiring mathematical calculations [12].

The interface features sliding inputs to specify the end-effector's planar Cartesian coordinates (X, Y) relative to the base frame along with the desired orientation angle Φ . The underlying inverse kinematics equations are implemented to compute the requisite joint angles ($\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$) for achieving the input pose. Manipulator joint variables are visually displayed in real-time as the pose parameters are modified [11].

To provide further insights, the GUI incorporates a graphical representation of the planar 3R manipulator using basic link and coordinate frame graphics. As the user interacts with the input slides, the visual model updates correspondingly to reflect the new configuration of the manipulator driven by the changing joint angles. This enables the user to intuitively visualize and verify the computed joint configurations [10] [11].

The integrated GUI allows rapid synthesis of various end-effector poses and instant visualization of the manipulator behavior. By providing an easy-to-use tool abstracted from the mathematical computations, the GUI can significantly facilitate analysis and development of kinematic relationships, control strategies, and motion planning algorithms. The availability of such interactive tools can complement theoretical kinematics studies with applied insights and serve pedagogical purposes for robotics education [14] [15].

Fig 6. GUI of the position kinematics

Dynamic Modeling of a 3R Robotic Manipulator

Dynamic modeling in robotics is the process of creating mathematical models that describe the motion and behavior of robotic systems. These models capture the dynamics and kinematics of robots, allowing for the analysis, control, and simulation of their movements [13].

Forward Dynamics

The forward dynamics model predicts the robot's motion based on the forces and torques applied to its joints. It calculates the resulting joint accelerations, velocities, and positions over time. This information helps in understanding how the robot will move in response to specific inputs or control signals.

Inverse Dynamics

The inverse dynamics model, on the other hand, determines the forces and torques required at the robot's joints to achieve a desired motion or trajectory. It is used for motion planning, trajectory generation, and robot control. By knowing the desired motion, the inverse dynamics model can calculate the forces and torques needed to achieve that motion.

Dynamic Modeling of a 3R Robotic Manipulator

Finding the mathematical dynamic model of a 3R robotic manipulator involves several steps. Here's a general outline of the process:

- Define the Robot's Kinematic Structure: Specify the geometric parameters of the 3R manipulator, such as the lengths of the three links and the position of the joints in a chosen reference frame. This information is essential for deriving the dynamic equations.
- Derive the Kinematic Equations: Use the Denavit-Hartenberg (DH) convention or any other suitable method to derive the forward kinematic equations of the 3R manipulator. This involves determining the transformation matrices that relate the joint angles to the position and orientation of the end-effector.
- Determine the Jacobian Matrix: Calculate the Jacobian matrix of the manipulator, which relates the end-effector velocities to the joint velocities. The Jacobian matrix provides a linear approximation of the manipulator's kinematics.
- Derive the Kinematic Differential Equations: Apply the time derivative to the forward kinematic equations derived in Step 2 to obtain the kinematic differential equations. These equations describe the relationship between joint velocities and end-effector velocities.
- Define the System's Lagrangian: The Lagrangian of a mechanical system combines the kinetic and potential energy terms. Write down the Lagrangian of the 3R manipulator using the kinetic and potential energy expressions for each link.
- Apply the Lagrange's Equations: Apply Lagrange's equations to the Lagrangian derived in Step 5 to obtain the dynamic equations of the 3R manipulator. These equations describe the system's dynamics and incorporate the effects of inertia, gravity, and applied forces or torques.
- Solve the Dynamic Equations: Solve the dynamic equations obtained in Step 6 to find the equations of motion for the 3R manipulator. This typically involves obtaining a set of coupled second-order differential equations.
- Simplify and Linearize the Equations: Depending on the complexity of the system and the desired analysis, simplifications and linearization may be applied to make the equations more manageable. This step may involve neglecting certain terms or approximating the system's behavior around a specific operating point.
- Validate and Verify the Model: Validate the dynamic model by obtaining the torques by putting values in the equations and comparing them with the torque provided by using the MATLAB tool SIM MECHANICS. Verify that the model accurately represents the behavior of the 3R manipulator.

Dynamic modeling is a powerful tool for analyzing, controlling, and simulating robotic systems. The dynamic model of a 3R robotic manipulator can be obtained by following the steps outlined above [12]. The model can then be used for a variety of tasks, such as motion planning, trajectory generation, and robot control.

Dynamic Modeling Using the MATLAB Toolbox SIM MECHANICS

SIM MECHANICS is a toolbox in MATLAB that enables the modeling, simulation, and analysis of mechanical systems. It uses a block diagram approach to represent and simulate the dynamics of these systems.

To use SIM MECHANICS to model the dynamic behavior of a 3R robotic manipulator, the following steps are typically followed:

Import the CAD Model: The first step is to import the CAD model of the 3R robotic manipulator into SIM MECHANICS. This can be done using the import cad function.

Define the System Dynamics: Once the CAD model has been imported, the next step is to define the system dynamics. This involves assigning appropriate physical properties to the components, such as mass, inertia, and geometry. Input forces or torques acting on the system can also be defined at this stage.

Simulate the Model: Once the system dynamics have been defined, the model can be simulated using the sim function. This will generate the time-domain response of the system, including the joint velocities, accelerations, and torques.

Advantages of Using SIM MECHANICS for Dynamic Modeling

There are several advantages to using SIM MECHANICS for dynamic modeling of robotic manipulators:

Ease of Use: SIM MECHANICS provides a user-friendly interface for modeling and simulating mechanical systems. This makes it relatively easy to learn and use, even for users with limited experience in robotics.

Accuracy: SIM MECHANICS uses a sophisticated physics engine to simulate the dynamics of mechanical systems. This results in highly accurate simulations that can be used to predict the real-world behavior of robotic systems.

Flexibility: SIM MECHANICS is a highly flexible tool that can be used to model a wide variety of mechanical systems, including robotic manipulators with different kinematic structures and actuators.

Table 3: Torques obtained by using SIM MECHANICS are:

Motor 1:	Motor 2:	Motor 3:
(0.342 ----- 0.399) Nm	(0.153 ----- 0.178) Nm	(0.036 ----- 0.042) Nm
(3.495 ----- 4.078) Kg.cm	(1.558 ----- 1.818) Kg.cm	(0.366 ----- 0.427) Kg.cm

Circuit designing

Circuit design involves systematically integrating electrical components to produce a practical device. The first step in this process is evaluating components based on their project requirements. To provide functionality, components are purchased and integrated. The diagram shows our circuit design.

Control Mechanisms

In this study, we integrate two pivotal control methods:

PID Control: Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) control is a prominent feedback control algorithm aiming to regulate system output by continuously modulating a control variable. This modulation is based on the disparity between the intended set-point and the observed output. Its application is ubiquitous, spanning areas such as robotics, automation, and process control.

Proportional Control (P): This component outputs a value proportional to the prevailing error. It multiplies the error signal by a proportional gain (Kp), effectively reducing the steady-state error and offering a prompt response to error fluctuations.

Structure: The control signal encompasses both the feed-forward and PID terms:

$$\text{Control signal} = \text{Feed - forward term} + \text{PID term}$$

The feed-forward method calculates the requisite control signal based on system characteristics and input reference, without relying on system output or error measurement. This term is derived using a system model or pre-existing knowledge of the system dynamics. Crucial to this process are:

System Knowledge: A mathematical model delineates the relationship between system input and output. System identification methods or known physical properties can procure this model.

Feed-forward Signal Determination: The feed-forward component is discerned by multiplying the reference input by a gain or transfer function extracted from the system model.

Integration into the Control Signal: This derived feed-forward component amalgamates with the PID control signal, ensuring comprehensive error and disturbance compensation.

Proportional Control (P) : This component outputs a value proportional to the prevailing error. It multiplies the error signal by a proportional gain (K_p), effectively reducing the steady-state error and offering a prompt response to error fluctuations.

$$P = K_p \times \text{error}$$

Integral Control (I): Focusing on the historical accumulation of errors, the integral component multiplies the integral of the error signal by an integral gain (K_i). This term eradicates steady-state errors that might linger with only proportional control.

$$I = K_i \times \int (\text{error } dt)$$

Derivative Control (D): This component anticipates future error trajectories by assessing the error's rate of change, multiplying this by a derivative gain (K_d). It thereby dampens system response, curtailing overshoot and preventing instability.

$$D = K_d \times \frac{d(\text{error})}{dt}$$

The Unified Effect of PID Control: All three components consolidate to produce the system's output:

$$\text{Output} = (K_p \times \text{Error}) + \left(K_i \times \int \text{error } dt \right) + \left(K_d \times \frac{d(\text{error})}{dt} \right)$$

PID control's widespread usage owes to its straightforwardness, efficacy across myriad control challenges, and robust tuning methodologies. Nonetheless, it might not cater to all systems, particularly those exhibiting nonlinear dynamics or pronounced time lags. Such systems might demand more intricate control approaches.

Feed-forward Control

Complementing the PID control, the feed-forward algorithm enhances control performance by anticipating and offsetting disturbances or variations in the system, furnishing a refined control signal.

Proportional gain values	Integral gain values	Derivative gain values
Kp1: 0.7	Ki1: 0.1	Kd1: 0.35
Kp2: 0.04309636660	Ki2: 0.0035	Kd2: 0.0827192733
Kp3: 0.10376256914779	Ki3: 0.06541114025	Kd3: 0.010558272085

Fig 7. Values obtained by combining PID and feed forward response

Image Processing: An Advanced Overview

Image processing is a pivotal element enabling computational systems to decipher visual data. This discipline commences with image acquisition via sensors or cameras. Subsequent phases involve preprocessing to enhance image quality by optimizing brightness and contrast while minimizing noise. Sophisticated feature extraction techniques are then utilized to discern pertinent visual attributes like textures, colors, and edges.

Camera Calibration and Object Detection in Computer Vision

Camera calibration is a crucial process in computer vision, enabling precise mapping between the 3D world and 2D images. Intrinsic parameters like focal length and lens distortion, along with extrinsic parameters defining camera positioning, play vital roles. Calibrating cameras involves analyzing recognizable patterns in images, like checkerboards, to estimate these parameters algorithmically. This calibration process offers multiple advantages, including precise measurements, object localization, and improved image processing for tasks like 3D reconstruction and object tracking. It also corrects lens distortions and facilitates the conversion of image coordinates to real-world metrics. Once calibrated, inferred parameters allow the projection of 3D coordinates onto 2D images for further analysis. Object detection, another aspect of computer vision, involves preprocessing images, extracting features, localizing objects, classifying them, and refining results, essential for identifying and delineating objects in images or videos.

Applications

Object detection is utilized in various sectors, including autonomous driving, surveillance systems, robotics, face detection, and image search. The technology allows for the identification and monitoring of items of interest in either real-time or recorded data. This capability greatly aids in many activities such as pedestrian recognition, object tracking, object counting within a given scene, and the ability to generate alerts for certain events.

Trajectory Optimization in Autonomous Systems

Path planning, a cornerstone of autonomous navigation, involves defining an optimal route from an initial to a terminal point while avoiding potential barriers. Central to robotics and autonomous vehicles, its primary objective is to devise a trajectory that adheres to benchmarks such as optimality, safety, and energy efficiency, taking into account environmental constraints and system capabilities.

Key Algorithms

Probabilistic Roadmap (PRM): Generates a graph of the navigational space by sampling configurations and linking them, facilitating efficient exploration of feasible paths.

Rapidly Exploring Random Tree (RRT): Constructs a tree by randomly sampling configurations, swiftly navigating towards feasible paths.

Potential Fields: Models robotic movement using potential energy fields, with forces either attracting the robot to goals or repelling it from obstacles. Primarily used in reactive planning.

Algorithm choice depends on the system's specifications, environmental factors, and desired performance.

Probabilistic Roadmap Methodology (PRM)

PRM involves:

- Sampling: Random configurations are derived from the navigational domain.
- Obstruction Verification: Configurations are assessed for collision risks, retaining only feasible ones.
- Configuration Synthesis: Viable configurations are linked based on proximity metrics.
- Roadmap Genesis: The resulting roadmap graph represents feasible robot trajectories.
- Trajectory Discovery: Paths are extracted from the roadmap using algorithms such as Dijkstra's or A* search, ensuring collision avoidance from start to end.

Fig 8. Obstacle free path using PRM

Trajectory Planning

Trajectory planning, or motion planning, determines a time-parameterized path for a system, taking into account constraints, goals, and system limitations. It aims to create an optimized trajectory meeting specific objectives like obstacle avoidance or energy conservation.

Key Steps in Trajectory Planning

Input and Constraints: Define parameters like starting and ending positions, velocities, and other system constraints.

Path Planning: Ascertain the geometric path from start to goal using algorithms like PRM or RRT.

Trajectory Generation: Compute a time-based trajectory from the chosen path using methods like polynomial interpolation or optimization-based techniques.

Constraints and Optimization: Ensure adherence to system and environmental constraints during trajectory generation.

Trajectory Refinement: Enhance the initial trajectory to improve performance, considering aspects like smoothness or velocity profiles.

Execution and Feedback: Execute the trajectory, using sensor feedback for real-time adjustments.

Trajectory Planning Method

The process begins with task definition, start and end points identification, and path planning algorithms to chart out the geometric path. This path is then time-parameterized, with desired velocity and acceleration profiles derived. Interpolation techniques, such as cubic spline interpolation, ensure smoothness.

Cubic Spline Interpolation

A favored method in robotics, cubic spline interpolation uses cubic polynomials to seamlessly link waypoints, offering control over position, velocity, and acceleration. After setting the trajectory waypoints, cubic polynomials are generated to interpolate them, ensuring a smooth trajectory transition. These third-degree equations control position, velocity, and acceleration, and are often utilized in joint space configurations.

Equation

Integrating the whole systems

Electronic and hardware components are assembled together. The figure of the integrated mechatronics system is given below:

Fig 9. Integrated 3R robotic manipulator

Results

In the realm of robotic manipulators, the term "3R" denotes an arm equipped with three rotational joints. This design enables the manipulator to operate in real-time, seamlessly receiving, processing, and reacting to incoming data or commands. The outcomes and advantages of such a 3R real-time robotic manipulator are largely influenced by its design nuances, inherent capabilities, and intended application. Here's a closer look at these benefits:

Dynamic Flexibility: Such manipulators are adept at agile movements and precise positioning. Their real-time functionality ensures they can promptly adjust to environmental changes or to feedback from sensors. This adaptability facilitates the execution of intricate tasks with unmatched precision and efficiency.

Rapid Responsiveness: The manipulator's real-time processing capability means it can instantly interpret and act upon input signals, thereby diminishing latency. This rapid responsiveness not only boosts task completion rates but also heightens overall productivity.

Safety First: With its ability to constantly monitor and instantaneously respond to safety parameters, this robotic manipulator significantly reduces accident risks. Whether it's detecting obstacles or recognizing hazardous situations, the manipulator modifies its motion accordingly to ensure a safe operational environment.

Collaborative Interactions: Real-time processing equips the manipulator to engage with its surroundings, humans, or other robots. In scenarios involving human-robot collaborations, for instance, the manipulator can real-time gauge and adapt to human intentions and movements.

Evolution Through Adaptive Control: These robotic manipulators can harness adaptive control methodologies or learning algorithms to perpetually refine their operations. By evaluating real-time feedback and tweaking their strategies or parameters, they can finetune movements, elevate precision levels, and adjust seamlessly to dynamic scenarios.

This revision emphasizes the benefits and capabilities of the 3R real-time robotic manipulator, making the content more coherent and impactful.

Limitations and Future Recommendations

Limitations

The 3R redundant planar serial COBOTS, while heralded for their flexibility and dexterity, do come with their own set of constraints. A brief rundown of these limitations includes:

Restricted Reach: These COBOTS, with their 3-degree-of-freedom (RRR) configuration, operate within a planar range, meaning they lack the capability to function in 3D space. The absence of bending capability further restricts their reach, confining object pickups to the direct level of the robot's end-effector.

Load Constraints: Their built-in motors lack the heft needed for lifting considerable weights.

Component Quality: Given that the predominant components used are of hobbyist-grade, there's an evident shortfall in accuracy and precision when juxtaposed with industrial-grade counterparts.

Lack of Force Sensing: The absence of force sensors implies these COBOTS can't send force feedback, thus sidelining the potential implementation of force-centric algorithms.

Manufacturing Flaws: Certain manufacturing discrepancies have led to altered dimensions, inducing unintentional bending. This, in turn, undermines the robot's stiffness, making the control of the first link a challenge.

However, it's crucial to remember that these limitations might not be universally applicable and can differ based on COBOT's specific design, execution, and use-case. Technological progression and enhanced control algorithms hold promise in mitigating some of these constraints.

Future Recommendations

- **Incorporate Force Sensors:** By integrating force sensors, COBOTS can generate force feedback, elevating their operational potential.
- **Embrace Dynamic Force Control:** Implementing dynamic force control or haptic feedback can substantially enhance COBOT's efficiency and tactile response.
- **Augment Lifting Capacity:** By employing heavier motors, the manipulator can be equipped to handle greater loads.
- **Sensing Fragility with Force Sensors:** Introducing force sensors at the gripper enables COBOT to discern and delicately handle fragile objects.

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